

IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTI-CHANNEL DISTRIBUTION AS AN ALTERNATIVE MARKETING CAPTURED FISH TO INCREASE THE INCOME OF FISHERMAN HOUSEHOLDS IN SOUTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

This research aims to provide understanding to fishermen as producers of marine fish commodities and marketing institutions about which marketing channels provide higher levels of profit than other channels. Furthermore, this research also aims to increase knowledge for producers to carry out product verification, so that the added value of goods is higher. With product improvements, of course the producer will have more business partners and in the end the sales volume will increase and business profits will also increase. This product diversification step is a manifestation of a change in producer behavior from catching directly selling (TLJ) to picking and selling behavior (POL). The results of this research found that the income received by marketing institutions involved in trading fresh sea fish commodities was influenced by the marketing functions carried out. The behavior of marketing institutions in each channel where the selling price of fish to consumers increases on average between 17.50% to 30.67%. The increase in selling prices for each institution is due to the treatment of the marketing function, among others; transportation functions, packing, cleaning, maintenance, preservation and so on. With the existence of alternative distribution of caught fish as a marketing activity to distribute from fishermen to final consumers with the aim of getting more expensive economic value. Collecting traders selling fish to retailers have incurred costs for several marketing functions, as well as other marketing institutions so that the price paid by final consumers is more expensive. The conclusion is that the longer the fish marketing distribution channel tends to be more expensive than the short marketing channel. However, you need to know that the application of marketing channels, both long and short, is influenced by the characteristics of the product being marketed.

Keywords: Business Behavior, Distribution Channels, Fishermen's Income.

INTRODUCTION

National development is carried out with the aim of achieving several targets at once, namely self-sufficiency in the fisheries sector, increasing foreign exchange earnings, increasing wider employment opportunities, increasing the income of fishing communities and utilizing and preserving natural resources nationally. Pangkep Regency was the area chosen because the area is known as a dominant source of livelihood for its people, especially fishermen. The average annual increase in production reached 2.11%. And or increased by an average of 203,024.62 tons/year

Fish production is increasing from year to year, of course this is an opportunity for marketing institutions to become marketing intermediaries from producers to final consumers in the hope of getting services through marketing margins. Increasing production as a concept is not only

seen from activities to increase the number of products physically produced, but all activities that add value to goods and services including the marketing system which is the lifeblood of a business mechanism (A. Harizt. 2001. p. 68). As experienced by producers (fishermen) is that production increases, but the sales value is often not significant with the level of income received.

The product marketing system in the marine fisheries sector is a very complex system, especially since there is the involvement of intermediary institutions (marketing institutions) to market them, each of which has different interests and methods. Methods and methods for marketing fish from fishermen to final consumers certainly require quite a lot of money. The costs incurred by both producers (fishermen) and marketing institutions will influence the high cost of goods sold and the selling price that consumers must pay. According to Kenneth, Kenneth, (2011), the amount of marketing costs differs from one another because; types of commodities, marketing locations, types and number of marketing institutions and the effectiveness of the marketing carried out. Marketing treatment as above directly harms fishermen/fishermen's households as the main source of income in the fresh wet fish business such as; lamuru fish, layan, sibula, skipjack, red snapper and rabbit fish and others. The process of distributing fish from producers (fishermen) to final consumers requires various functional marketing activities aimed at expediting the process of distributing goods (fish) effectively and efficiently to meet consumer needs and desires. The final consumers referred to here are local, regional consumers and inter-island entrepreneurs who are considered the final users of goods. The marketing function is carried out by marketing institutions that are related or involved in the marketing process of an item (fish) which forms a marketing chain or is often referred to as a marketing system.

Pangkep Regency is a research location with several marketing institutions involved in the fish trade mechanism, namely; local retail traders, Ponggawa (collecting traders including cooperatives), sub-district intermediary traders as agents, district wholesalers, inter-island wholesalers and exporter wholesalers. Marketing institutions involved in commodity trading have two functions, namely as buyers and sellers, so that in this pair relationship there is a sales function on the one hand and a buyer function on the other. The occurrence of these two functions of marketing institutions illustrates the transfer of property rights or control rights by each institution to fish commodities, thereby causing additional uses of ownership.

The mechanism for buying and selling fresh fish commodities caught by fishermen at sea from producers to intermediary traders (marketing institutions) consists of three types of transaction behavior, namely; (1) active-active type, namely each active between the seller (producer) and buyer, and usually this type occurs when fishermen have a production volume equal to demand, (2) active-passive type, namely active producers offering their production results due to an increase in production output, but buyers are less active, and usually this type occurs when supply is greater than demand, as a result prices are determined more by buyers including marketing institutions, (3) passive-active type, which is the opposite of the second type above, where buyers are more active in demanding goods (fish) and sellers (producers) are less active, which may be due to reduced production results, and usually the prevailing prices are more

influenced by producers. The buying and selling function, which is usually called the exchange function, is very important to reduce barriers to the transfer of property rights in an effort to provide satisfaction to consumers by considering effective and efficient marketing channels. With the change in ownership fish goods through an exchange function, then the above activities function to add value to ownership of the product. The final consumer will be willing to pay a certain amount of money equal to the value of the product, if the product is perceived and able to provide a satisfaction value commensurate with the money that must be spent, including service and product quality.

Fish trade with market quality standards is largely determined by the final consumer, so the role of marketing institutions is very necessary because the marketing function is mostly carried out by marketing institutions because they have sufficient capital to do so. With the costs incurred to meet the quality standards desired by consumers, the selling price determination also has an influence, or in other words, the price paid by consumers is more expensive than consumers going directly to producers (fishermen). Marketing functions related to product quality include; sorting/cleaning, storage, cooling, packaging and transportation. Meanwhile, others include product management discipline to avoid waste/damage. According to Avonina, S. (2010), the amount of marketing costs differs from one another because; types of commodities, marketing locations, types and number of marketing institutions and the effectiveness of the marketing carried out.

The high basic price that consumers have to pay will reduce the level of consumption and real income of consumers and consumers will tend to think of alternatives by substituting purchases for the needs of the goods to be purchased, such as buying fish at an expensive price, it is better to buy tofu/tempeh or eggs at a higher price. Affordable and high nutritional value.

RESEARCH METHODS

a. Research Location

The research was conducted in two districts, namely Pangkep Regency and Maros Regency, South Sulawesi Province with the basis for choosing these locations because these two areas are the areas that supply the largest number of sea and land fishery products among other regions. And another reason is that the majority of people depend on this sector for their livelihood, namely around 56.27% on average (source, BPS South Sulawesi Province in Figures 2010). Then, it is hoped that these two areas will be designated as research objects in the future, when the results of the research will be taken into consideration by the local government in preparing short and medium term development plans.

b. Population and Sample

The population in this study was to select several farmer-fisherman groups from both regions which had a minimum of 5-10 members. Based on statistical data for each of these two regions, 78 farmer-fisherman groups have been recorded, which means they have a membership population of ± 624 people, and if each member has a minimum of 3 family members, this means the number of people living in this sector is 1872 soul.

c. Types and Sources of Data

The data obtained in this research includes primary data sourced from empirical data directly collected from the research location through direct observation, interviews and distributing questionnaires. The next data is secondary data obtained through reviewing the literature in the form of books, journals and required documents related to the research.

d. Data Collection Techniques

The technique used to obtain data is to use several methods, namely; interviews, distributing questionnaires, and literature studies. The data collection method by distributing questionnaires is intended to find out and compile data about the volume of wet fish production and the sales value received as well as the level of profit after expenses for the production factors used. Meanwhile, the data obtained through interviews is how many marketing institutions are their business partners. And to what extent the level of marketing efficiency is relative to the chosen marketing channels. Meanwhile, data obtained through literature studies, journals and so on is knowledge that has research relevance.

e. Data analysis

Based on the data obtained from the research results, the following analysis can be made:

(1). Marketing margin.

To measure the size of the marketing margin at each marketing institution by the channels through which the product reaches the final consumer are:

$$M = B + \pi$$

Where :

M = Marketing margin

B = Marketing costs

Π = Profit

(Steven, 2011)

The total marketing margin can be determined by adding up the margins for each marketing institution involved in marketing wet fish, namely:

$$M = Y1 + Y2 + Y3 + \text{-----} Yn$$

Where :

M = Total margin

Y1 = Marketing margin at market level 1

Y2 = Marketing margin at market level 2

Y3 = Marketing margin at market level 3

Yn = Marketing margin at market level n

To calculate the profits of marketing institutions, the formula is used:

$$\Pi = TR - TC$$

Where:

Π = Profit from each marketing agency involved.

TR = Total revenue (total revenue for each marketing institution)

TC = Total costs incurred by marketing institutions.

(2). Marketing Efficiency

To measure the level of marketing efficiency, the formula is used:

$$EP = \frac{\text{Marketing Costs}}{\text{The value of the product being marketing}} \times 100 \%$$

(3). Analysis of factors that influence marketing margins

To determine the factors that influence marketing margin, multiple regression analysis is carried out with the formula:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + E_i$$

Where:

Y = Marketing margin

X1 = Marketing costs

X2 = Marketing profits

B₀ = Parameter to be estimated

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Post-Marketing Treatment of Marine Fish

So that the quality and smooth marketing of fresh sea fish is a routine business fishing community in Pangkep Regency, the marketing concept is the main factor that influences fishermen's income levels and needs special attention, so that the prices received by fishermen remain reasonable, so post-marketing treatment plays a very important role. In Pangkep Regency, it is the focus of research on the fresh sea fish trade, especially studies on the behavior of marketing institutions which influence fishermen's income levels and provide an illustration that post-marketing activities are carried out by fishermen only at the initial stage, namely fishermen only carry out fishing at sea, preservation, transportation and sale in fresh form. Meanwhile, the sorting, cleaning, preservation, packing and transportation stages are generally carried out by marketing institutions.

To carry out efficient post-marketing, fishermen must change their marketing patterns from mono-channel to multi-channel. The findings obtained in this study are the existence of a mono-channel marketing system, where some fishermen have regular subscriptions to intermediary traders who are usually called ponggawa, where this institution provides capital/loans to fishermen in need in advance with business contracts for the fish caught by the fishermen.

Sell to the intermediary trader. In this type of business contract model, prices are generally determined by the trader and tend to be less profitable for fishermen. For details on post-marketing treatment of fresh sea fish, see the following chart:

Figure 1: Post-Marketing Treatment of Fresh Sea Fish

Post-marketing activities are generally carried out by marketing institutions, including retailers, collecting traders, wholesalers, agents and inter-island traders with more work being done by their workforce. Meanwhile, fishermen as producers of fresh fish they catch prefer to sell it directly to intermediaries or marketing institutions and carry out less marketing functions. This is done because fishermen have several limitations such as; time and costs to carry out the marketing process, so that the price paid from intermediary traders is not significant in relation to the income received. Marketing in principle is the flow of goods from producers to consumers. This flow of goods can occur because of the role of marketing institutions, where the role of these institutions is very dependent on the prevailing market system and the characteristics of the flow of goods being marketed. Therefore, this concept is often termed marketing channels, whose function is very important, especially in looking at price levels in each marketing institution.

Table 1: Activities of marketing functions carried out at various levels of behavior of fresh sea fish marketing institutions

No.	Behavior	Activity
01.	Fisherman	- <i>Fishing</i> - <i>Storage</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sale</i>
02.	Collector	- <i>Purchase</i> - <i>Cleaning</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sale</i>
03.	Wholesaler at TPI	- <i>Purchasing</i> - <i>Sorting</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Packing</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sale</i>
04.	Retailer	- <i>Purchasing</i> - <i>Sorting</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Sale</i>

Table 1. above, it can be seen that post-marketing activities by implementing marketing functions are generally carried out by marketing institutions so that the costs incurred directly increase, thus affecting the total cost per unit of product/fish. In this description, it appears that in the marketing process from producers to final consumers, marketing institutions have an important role in the trade of fresh sea fish which has benefits and interests for all parties, including increasing local income and employment opportunities.

b. Marine Fish Marketing Channels

Marketing of sea fish, especially fresh fish which is usually called wet fish (from the sea) and land fish (pond fish) in Pangkep Regency, there are several marketing institutions in the process of being transferred from producers to final consumers. There are several traders/intermediary marketing institutions involved in the marketing process, namely; (1) collecting traders/ponggawa, (2) commissioners, (3) wholesalers, (4) retailers/pagangang to final consumers. Fishermen as producers of fresh sea fish (wet fish) generally search for fish in the sea day and night by catching, preserving, transporting and then selling them to marketing institutions/intermediary traders in baskets. For more details, the marketing channel for wet fish (sea fish) in Pangkep Regency is the place for marketing institutions and final consumers. Business costs and income. The marine fish commodity in the fisheries and marine sector is the main source of income for the majority of the population of Pangkep Regency, where this area is known as one of the areas that has many fishing islands, hence the name Pangkep Islands. The marketing channels through which the marine fish trade passes in Pangkep Regency are as follows:

Picture. 2. Marine Fish Marketing Channels

Channel I

Analysis of costs, margins and profits on this channel can be seen in table 2. Below:

Table 2: Analysis of costs, margins and income at collector level traders (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru Fish	Snapper	Layan Fish	Sibula Fish	Skipjack Fish	Baronan Fish
01.	Purchases	22.500	17.500	9.100	2.250	15.000	27.000
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637	157,70	1.050	-
	• Sorting	1.350	875	364	90,00	600	-
	• Preservation	1.125	700	-	-	450	2.160
	• Packing	2.250	525	-	-	300	810
	• Storage	-	350	-	-	-	-
03.	Total costs	8.725	5.425	1.911	332	3.900	4.320
04.	Cost price	31.225	22.925	11.011	2.582	18.900	31.320
05.	Sales price	37.470	28.656	14.314	3.099	22.680	40.716
06.	Income	6.245	5.731	3.303	516	3.780	9.396
07.	Marketing margin	14.970	11.156	5.214	849	7.680	13.716
08.	Mark-up	20,540	25,190	30,320	17,50	28,88	30,67

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 2. Above provides an illustration of the income received by intermediary traders/collectors, there are several types of fish where marketing functions are not carried out, but this does not affect the level of income but tends to increase, such as for baronan fish and lamuru fish. The behavior of marketing/collecting institutions in this channel has determined sales prices to increase between 17.50% to 30.67%. Furthermore, the analysis of costs, margins and income for sub-district wholesalers can be seen in table 3 below:

Table 3: Cost, Margin and Income Analysis at District Wholesaler Level (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru Fish	Snapper	Layan Fish	Sibula Fish	Skipjack Fish	Baronan Fish
01.	Purchases	37.470	28.656	14.314	3.099	22.680	40.716
02.	Marketing Costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	-	-	668	164	-	-
	• Sorting	1.417	918	382	94	-	-
	• Preservation	1.181	735	715	154	1.134	2.203
	• Packing	2.362	551	750	161	315	850
	• Storage	374	357	286	61	453	814
03.	Total cost	7.834	4.311	3.711	859	3.402	8.217
04.	Cost price	45.304	32.967	18.025	3.958	26.082	48.933
05.	Sales price	49.834	36.263	19.828	4.354	28.690	53.826
06.	Income	4.530	3.296	1.803	396	2.607	4.893
07.	Marketing margin	12.364	7.607	5.514	1.255	6.010	13.110
08.	Mark-up	10,00	12,32	10,02	10,05	9,20	15,59

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 3 above contains several treatments for the types of fish processed by sub-district wholesalers which are related to marketing functions such as sorting and packing activities so that the costs incurred by these marketing institutions quite influence the level of income. Then, these wholesalers make sales margins to district/city wholesalers of between 10% and 15.59%. When compared with the activities of marketing functions between collecting traders and sub-district wholesalers, more collectors do it, so there is a difference in the percentage increase in selling prices, in this case it is higher received by collectors. Furthermore, analysis of costs, margins and income levels for district/city wholesalers can be seen in table 4 below:

Table 4: Analysis of Costs, Margins and Income for Regency Wholesalers (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru Fish	Snapper	Layan Fish	Sibula Fish	Skipjack Fish	Baronan Fish
01.	Purchases	49.834	36.263	19.828	4.354	28.690	53.826
02.	Marketing Costs:						
	• Transpor	2.750	1.925	910	1.001	1.650	1.485
	• Cleaning	2.493	1.813	701	172	1.435	2.691
	• Sorting	1.445	963	401	99	574	1.076
	• Preservation	997	725	715	396	573	538
	• Packing	498	557	758	163	318	859
	• Storage	382	363	292	63	462	830
03.	Total cost	8.565	6.346	3.133	1.894	5.012	7.479
04.	Cost price	58.399	42.609	22.961	6.248	33.702	61.305
05.	Sales price	63.655	46.870	25.716	6.873	38.757	72.033
06.	Income	5.256	4.261	2.755	625	5.055	10.728
07.	Marketing margin	13.821	10.607	6.888	2.519	10.067	18.207
08.	Mark-up	9,19	11,19	15,00	10,00	10,00	12,00

Table 4 above describes marketing activities to sub-district wholesalers, namely after purchasing fresh sea fish from collectors then carrying out several marketing function activities by paying different amounts of total costs for each type of fish. The difference in total costs incurred directly affects the level of income and margin received by sub-district wholesalers, however, the mark-up level is between 9.19% and 15%. Paying attention to the results of the analysis of expenditure and income obtained by this marketing institution is not too far from that of collecting traders. Based on the results of an interview with the head of the marine fish traders group in Labbakang Regency, Dg. Jamal, he said that the price increase applied to consumers, both industry, retailers and household consumers, was not too high with an average of 12%. Furthermore, analysis of costs, margins and income at retail level traders can be seen in table 5 below:

Table 5: Cost, Margin and Revenue Analysis at Retailer Level

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru Fish	Snapper	Layan Fish	Sibula Fish	Skipjack Fish	Baronan Fish
01.	Purchases	63.655	46.870	25.716	6.873	38.757	72.033
02.	Marketing Costs:						
	• Transpor	638	469	257	69	387	720
	• Cleaning	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Sorting	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Preservation	1.007	732	722	400	543	578
	• Packing	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Retribution	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200
03.	Total cost	2.845	2.401	2.179	1.669	2.130	2.498
04.	Cost price	66.500	49.271	27.895	8.542	40.887	74.531
05.	Sales price	73.150	54.198	33.474	8.969	44.976	81.984
06.	Income	6.650	4.927	5.579	427	4.089	7.453
07.	Marketing margin	9.495	7.328	7.758	2.096	6.219	9.951
08.	Mark-up	10,00	10,00	15,00	9,00	10,00	10,00

Table 5 above, after processing the results data on marketing activities carried out by retailers, has obtained analysis results, namely, where this marketing institution (retailer) has three marketing activities carried out, namely; transportation of goods, preservation and levies and all three of them incur costs as described in table 5. Then, with the expenditure paid to these three marketing functions, the level of income obtained by retailers decreases so it can be concluded that the more marketing functions are carried out by marketing institutions then the costs of the marketing process also increase so that the retailer's income/profit level decreases.

Channel II

In the marine fish marketing structure, it appears that producers and marketing institutions have distance and time to the final consumer, including the costs incurred by each marketing institution to deliver the product/fish being marketed based on the channels traversed. This second channel involves two marketing institutions, including; collectors and dealers. For greater clarity, the following can be described quantitatively regarding the total costs, margins and level of income obtained by each institution in table 6 as follows:

Table 6: Cost, Margin and Revenue Analysis at Collector to Retailer Level (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchases	22.500	17.500	9.100	2.250	15.000	27.000
02.	Marketing Costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637	157,70	1.050	-
	• Sorting	1.350	875	364	90,00	600	-
	• Preservation	1.125	700	-	-	450	2.160
	• Packing	2.250	525	-	-	300	810
	• Storage	-	350	-	-	-	-
03.	Total cost	8.725	5.425	1.911	332	3.900	4.320
04.	Cost price	31.225	22.925	11.011	2.582	18.900	31.320
05.	Sales price	40.593	29.802	18.186	2.840	20.790	34.452
06.	Income	9.368	6.877	7.175	258	1.890	3.132
07.	Marketing	18.093	12.302	9.086	590	5.790	7.452
08.	Mark-up	30.00	30.00	15.25	10.17	28.88	30.67

Table 6 above provides an illustration that the level of income obtained by collecting traders is higher than through the first channel. This happens because this channel is short and the selling price is more expensive because the purchasing volume of retailers is smaller than the purchasing volume of sub-district wholesalers. Meanwhile, the cost price and sales price have a mark-up of between 10.17% and 30.67% with different profit levels based on the marketing functions carried out by each marketing institution.

c. Margin and Revenue

Marketing of fresh sea fish production obtained by fishermen through several marketing channels results in different results or business profits for each marketing institution due to marketing function activities, time and costs incurred. This can be seen at the level of margin and income for each marketing channel in table 7 as follows:

Table 7: Analysis of Margin and Revenue in Channel I

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1.	Collector Trader	37.470	6.245	8.725	14.970
2.	District Large Traders	49.834	4.530	7.834	12.364
3.	Regency/city wholesalers	63.655	5.256	8.565	13.821
4.	Retailers	73.150	6.650	2.845	9.495
	Total		22.681	27.969	50.650

Table 7 above describes the amount of income and marketing margin for each channel through which goods/fresh sea fish reach the final consumer. The highest sales price in this channel is at the retail level at IDR 73,150/kg, while the highest margin level is at the collecting trader. The difference in margin income for each channel is due to the activities of marketing

functions, costs and the number of marketing institutions. The collecting traders are at the forefront as intermediary traders between producers/fishermen and other intermediary traders so that this marketing institution has many marketing function activities which can be seen in table 1. Furthermore, analysis of margin and income in channel II in table 8 is as follows:

Table 8: Analisis Marjin dan Pendapatan pada Saluran II

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Revenue (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1.	Collector Traders	40.593	9.368	8.725	18.093
2.	Retailers	54.582	9.084	4.825	13.909
Total			18.452	13.550	32.002

Table 8 above provides an illustration that differences in margins, costs and income levels of each marketing institution in each channel are caused by the treatment of the marketing function. For example, collecting traders selling fish to retailers have incurred costs of IDR 8,725/kg and the sales level is IDR. 40,593/kg. Meanwhile, at the retailer level, the selling price has been set at Rp. 54,582/kg, but the costs incurred were Rp. 4,825/kg so there is a cost difference of Rp. 3,900/kg between collecting traders and retailers. Next, the margin and income analysis in channel III can be seen as follows:

Table 9: Channel III Margin and Revenue Analysis

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1.	Collector Trader	63.655	18.237	4.825	9.159
2.	Regency/City Wholesalers	73.203	4.530	7.834	12.364
3.	Retailer	78.752	10.272	4.825	15.097
Total			33.039	17.484	36.620

Table 9 above provides an illustration that the level of expensive sales is at retailers because the goods/fish received are at the third level from producers. With the stages that goods go through to the final consumer through wholesalers and retailers, the price received by consumers is IDR 78,752 with costs of IDR. 4,825/kg. Meanwhile, the lowest margin level is at the collecting trader level, but the income level is the highest. This occurs because the marketing function is treated more than other marketing institutions. For channel IV with margin and income levels, see the following table:

Table 10: Margin and Revenue Analysis at the Channel IV Retailer Level

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1	Producer - Retailer-				
2	To final Consumer	49.214	8.202	7.262	15.404

d. Marketing Channel Efficiency

Marketing efficiency is basically the ratio of marketing output to input. Marketing output is the final sales result received, while marketing input is the funds used to process and transport the product so that it arrives in the hands of consumers.

The efficiency of marketing channels for fresh sea fish from producers to consumers in the Pangkep area to other areas can be seen in table 11 below:

Table 11: Efficiency and Profits of Fresh Sea Fish Marketing Channels in Pangkep Regency

No.	Channel	Efficiency (%)	Profit (Rp/Kg)
1.	I	38,25	22.681
2.	II	24,83	18.452
3.	III	22,20	33.039
4.	IV	14,75	8.202

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 11 above shows that the income from marketing fresh sea fish in channel III is IDR 33,039/kg with an efficiency level of 22.20%, while the lowest income is in channel IV amounting to IDR 8,202. There is an assessment of the level of marketing efficiency for fresh sea fish products to find out which channel is more efficient by getting a greater level of profit, although in theory it says that a short marketing channel is an efficient one, but in this study it has been found that the efficient channel is the which results in a higher level of profit.

CONCLUSION

In this research, after being carried out, several study results have been obtained using a matrix cost, margin and income analysis approach so that it can be concluded temporarily as follows:

- 1) The costs, margins and income levels of each marketing agency are different.
- 2) The level of income earned by marketing institutions differs from each other.
- 3) Marketing efficiency of agricultural and fisheries sector products through short marketing channels.
- 4) The high marketing margin for each channel is influenced by the activities of marketing functions.
- 5) The marketing function influences the level of product quality and increases sales volume.

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